

The Relationship Between Role Conflict and Emotional Intelligence towards Work-Life Balance: An Indian Context

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Work-life balance and emotional intelligence is a set of skills generally denoted as interpersonal or intrapersonal skills or soft skills that are not enclosed under the traditional areas. This paper emphasizes how emotional intelligence and work-life balance are associated with each other. A few researchers found that ability to observe, control, and assess emotions can be well-educated and strengthened.

Methods: This study has 408 samples by using a purposive sample technique. A structured measurement scale was circulated. The researcher constructs the conceptual framework with the help of previous literature. Analysis was done and validate the constructed hypotheses.

Findings: The result explores that there is an impact of quality of work-life on employee retention and job satisfaction among the faculty members in higher education institutions. The result states that role conflict and emotional intelligence are positively related to work-life balance.

Keywords: Work-life balance, Role Conflict, Emotional Intelligence, Higher Education Institutions

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for work currently made the work-life balance problem broadly deliberated in this present competitive environment (Omaret *et al.*, 2015). In higher competition circumstances, this stresses institutions to modify their strategies which necessitate employees to have high involvement in their job (Hamidi, 2005). Likewise, the high competition also will provide affect the quality of service delivery by the employee (Nwagbara & Akanji, 2012). Based on the demand, the present job has been quickly

changing as related to the existing years, employers constantly find it is an interesting effort to offer jobs with a balance between quality of work and family (Nadeem & Abbas, 2009). Work-life balance was defined by Lockwood (2003) as the same level of satisfying the wants of both individual's job and private life. This creates employees facing problems and conflicts whether to provide insistence on work or family life (Jamadinet *al.*, 2015). The conflict between the interest in work and life has prompted representative's pressure in adjusting both which are expected to be executed simultaneously. Skilful and capable human power is one of the most wanted and fundamental parts that assist organizations with accomplishing their targets and objectives. In any case, 21st-century working environments have become profoundly cut throat and representatives are under constant pressure to improve.

Thus, the focal point of human asset supervisors has been moving towards ideas like representative prosperity, Work-Life Balance (WLB), and so on as they lead to an upgrade in workers' proficiency and efficiency. Among these, representative prosperity which is extensively characterized by Grant *et al.* (2007) as the general nature of a representative's encounter and working at work has three center aspects, specifically mental, physical, and social prosperity. WLB is "the singular discernment that work and non-work exercises are viable and advance development as per a singular's on going life needs" (Kalliath and Brough, 2008).

Research Objectives

1. to examine the relationship between role conflict and emotional intelligence among the faculty members
2. to identify the influence of role conflict and emotional intelligence on work-life balance

2. LITERARY REVISED

2.1 Role Conflict

Role conflict has been tested because simultaneously there are at least two jobs that should be satisfied. Omar *et al.*, (2015) concurred that once there are inconsistent requests drawn in upon a worker, it shows that the representatives are engaged with role conflict. Moreover, there are four groupings of role conflict. First, role conflict happens when singular cravings are divergent with different workers. Second, when assumptions on a similar job got from at least two individuals are tangled or known as inter-sender conflict (Ritteret *al.*, 2016). The third classification was an inter-role conflict which happens when numerous particular jobs should be locked in by representatives simultaneously. The contention of Intra source happens when there is contrariness between the designed job and the role set of an individual like their assets and capacities (Dorrelet *al.*, 2014). Sariat *al.*, (2017) characterized role conflict as the irregularity of necessities from the job, where consistency is decided about because of circumstances that give influence job execution. Moreover, an unmistakable job of representatives ought to be particular to stay away from the job of contention which will request investment to oversee work and family (Duxbury & Higgins, 2001).

2.2 Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence refers to the value in anybody on a significant level and suggests the ability to see, control, and evaluate sentiments. Some researchers recommend that ability to comprehend people on a significant level can be learned and invigorated, while others promise it is an inborn characteristic. Emotional intelligence consists of five factors: knowing one's emotions,

motivating oneself, managing emotions, recognizing emotions with others, and handling relationship. Emotional intelligence more profound level deals with individual and progressive execution. It plays a significant work in the kind of work a delegate produces and the relationship the individual values in the organization. Emotional Intelligence is qualities and capabilities that capture a wide assembly of individual dispositions and skills, generally referred to as soft skills, intelligence, and professional skills. Work-life balance is explained as an agreeable level of contribution or fit between the multiple roles in a person's life. In this climate managing, the boundary between home and work is becoming more challenging. Organizations need to ensure that they were engaging as well as request a feasible and useful harmony among fun and serious exercises system, benefiting and tending to the necessities of both the affiliation and its delegates.

2.3 Work-Life Balance

The term 'work-life balance' was first used in the late 1970s to portray the harmony between an individual's work and individual life. During that time, the universe of work changed from an all-day issue to 24 hours, 7 days week system, and saw expanded ladies' cooperation in the labor force and double-worker couples (Voydanoff, 1987). Work-life balance quickly became famous due to the unique work environment changes and turned into a worldwide peculiarity (Ashwini, 2017). This brought about the development of the idea of work-life balance which was progressively viewed as a worry for the two representatives and bosses (Guest, 2002). In a review demonstrating the all-encompassing perspective on work-life balance, Sirgy and Lee (2018) separated the results of work-life balance into three sections: work-related outcomes, non-work-related outcomes, and stress-related outcomes. In another review, Vajiravel (2015) expressed that the beneficial outcomes of appropriate work-life balance incorporate superior representative efficiency and assurance, work inspiration, work fulfillment, further developed ailments, and enough time for individual and everyday life while work-life conflict, work pressure, non-attendance, close to home weariness, high turnover, work exchanging, workaholism and medical problems are some of the adverse consequences of an in work life.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 *Sample Method:*

The sample was drawn by using the cluster sampling method. There are six arts and science colleges were chosen as a population. From the population, the researcher has got responses from 394 samples. The structured measurement scale was used to gather the primary data from the targeted respondents.

3.2 *Measures and Tools:*

The measures were taken from pre-defined items in the previous studies. The first part deals with the demographic profile of the respondents. Followed by role conflict has 7- items adapted from Flaherty *et al.*, (1999), emotional intelligence has 33-items which are derived from Wang (2002), and work-life balance has 15-items adapted from Fisher-Mc Auley *et al.*, (2003). The data were collected through an online mode by using google forms. After the data collection, the analysis was made with appropriate statistical tools like percentage analysis, mean, standard deviation, ANOVA, and correlation analysis were performed. By using these tools, the hypothesis was tested in this study.

3.3 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is framed with the support of a literature review of previous studies.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework Model

3.4 Hypotheses Development:

H₁: Role Conflict is positively and significantly related to Work-Life Balance

H₂: Emotional Intelligence is positively and significantly related to Work-Life Balance

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: Demographics of the Respondents

Category	Item	Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	187	48.8
	Female	207	51.2
Age (in years)	Less than 30	74	19.3
	31 - 40	100	23.2
	41 - 50	137	35.7
	51 and above	83	21.7
Discipline	Arts	179	43.8
	Science	215	56.1
Working as	Aided	187	45.9
	Self - Finance	207	54.1
Experience (in years)	Less than 5	98	33.7
	6 - 10	103	26.8
	11 - 15	124	32.3
	16 and above	69	18.0

Source: Field Data

Out of 394 respondents, 187 males and 207 females have participated in this survey. 74 respondents opted to be less than 30 years old, 100 respondents opted to be 31 - 40 years old, 137 respondents opted to be 41 - 50 years old, and 83 respondents opted to be 51 and above years old. 179 respondents belong to the arts discipline and 215 respondents belong to the science discipline. 187 respondents were working as aided professors and 207 respondents were working as self-finance professors. 98 respondents have less than 5 years of experience, 103 respondents have 6 - 10 years of experience, 124 respondents have 11 - 15 years of experience, and 69 respondents have 16 and above years of experience.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	sd	Alpha
Role conflict with Work-life balance	2.5482	0.7689	0.914
Emotional intelligence with Work-life balance	3.4877	1.0815	0.857

All the subscales were found to have a high rate of reliability with Cronbach alphas which are greater than the standard level of 0.7.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy	0.714
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Approx. Chi-Square	913.123
df	72
Sig	0.000

Table 3: ANOVA

Variable		Sum of Square	df	f.test	p-value
Role Conflict	Between Groups	3.348	5	0.668	0.024
	Within Groups	148.883	389		
	Total	152.231	394		
Emotional Intelligence	Between Groups	2.415	5	0.782	0.041
	Within Groups	123.155	389		
	Total	125.570	394		

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Work-Life Balance	Between Groups	6.691	5	0.829	0.542
	Within Groups	252.697	389		
	Total	259.387	394		

Table 4: Correlation among the Dimensions

Variable	Role Conflict	Emotional Intelligence	Work-Life Balance
Role Conflict	0.30**		
Emotional Intelligence	0.83	0.27**	
Work-life Balance	0.65**	0.72*	0.67*

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); and * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

There is a positive and significant relationship between role conflict and work-life balance which is significant at a 0.01 level. Emotional intelligence has a significant relationship with work-life balance which is statistically significant at a 0.05 level. Hence, the constructed hypotheses were supported statistically in nature.

5. CONCLUSION

The work-life conflict has severe consequences on the employees and organizations too. So employing employees with good emotional intelligence would be an initial step to minimizing this conflict and dropping the turnover. Likewise, the demographic changes fashionable in the workforce are essential also to be measured by institutions as their appearance is at stake. Now younger people and a mass number of females too are arriving in the labor force so institutions must test their emotional quotient along with intelligence quotient as a method of enrolment to diminish turnover and have good working circumstances. It was recognized that Work-Family Life is a significant factor in job performance and one of the reasons for employee turnover. Emotional intelligence has an important effect on a person's work-life balance and donates considerably towards keeping a proper balance in professional and personal life. Institutions should come up with efficient and effective work-life balance strategies and programs and organizational culture that motivates the utilization of available policies. This will help minimize the work-life conflict. Institutions must take initiative to progress the emotional intelligence capabilities of their employees as it shows a substantial role in the kind of work an employee produces and the connection that enjoys in the institutions and develop individual and institutional performance. The pressure of deadlines has pressed faculty members to work longer hours as the workload is comprehensively augmented during peak season.

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